

Factors Influencing the Fluctuation of Exchange Rate: A Study in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the factors affecting the fluctuation of exchange rate in Bangladesh. The study area is confined to only Bangladesh and study period is from January 2012 to December 2016 that means 60 months data of all variable has been collected. Some statistical analyses are conducted such as descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression. Descriptive statistics shows minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of all variables. To find out the strength and direction of relationship between variables, correlation analysis is conducted. The impact of each independent variable on exchange rate is analyzed through regression. All of this statistical analysis is conducted through SPSS-16 software. Here exchange rate is considered as a dependent variable and inflation, interest rate, balance of payment, balance of trade, remittance, export and import as independent variables. Exchange rate is taken BDT against US\$. Some other factors have impact on exchange rate such as gross domestic product, government debt, government regulation, political stability and performance, recession and speculation etc. Along with the relationship and impact of independent variables on dependent variable, recent trend and its comparison with some neighboring countries are presented. The result of correlation analysis shows significant positive relationship of inflation, interest rate and balance of payment with exchange rate. Inflation also shows strong positive relationship with exchange rate that indicates if inflation changes, exchange rate changes by the same changing pattern. On the other hand, the strength of relationship of interest rate and balance of payment with exchange rate is weak. Export and import of Bangladesh indicates significant negative correlation with exchange rate and the strength of association is moderate. There is no significant relationship of remittance and balance of trade with exchange rate. The regression model shows that inflation has greater impact on exchange rate than any other specified independent variables.

Keywords: Descriptive Statistics, Correlation, Regression, Scatter Plo.

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INTRODUCTION

Exchange rate is termed as the current market price for which one currency can be traded for another. As exchange rate plays such an important role in a country's competitiveness level, currency exchange rates are among the most analyzed and forecasted indicators in the world. To maintain the macroeconomic stability there is no fixed rules to select most suitable exchange rate. The specific feature of every country influences the choice of an appropriate exchange rate system. The developed country adopts the free floating exchange rate may not be appropriate for some developing country whose economy is not able to handle the risk of exchange rate volatility and the market of insurance is not so well developed. There are four types of exchange rate system such as fixed, freely floating, managed float and pegged types. In past, pegged exchange rate regimes or fixed exchange rate regimes was maintained by Bangladesh. On May 31, 2003, Bangladesh started to maintain floating exchange rate system by leaving the modifiable pegged system in order to ascertain the actual value of foreign currencies when market forces (demand and supply) regulate their value, not the central bank. In macroeconomic policies of Bangladesh, management of exchange rate is central issues. For the last two years sustained stability of exchange rate has been a foundation of the government careful management in Bangladesh. Until the end of 2015, nominal exchange rate of Bangladeshi Taka relative to US dollar has not been changed by remaining stable at Tk. 77.8 for one US dollar (Financial Express). The exchange rate is determined by the level of supply and demand on the international markets. However, changes in foreign exchange market rates are often difficult to understand and to predict because the market is very large and volatile. The demand and supply of currency is influenced by some specific factors such as export, import, interest rate, inflation rate, and remittance, balance of payment, balance of trade and GDP. So these are called the influencing factors of exchange rate. Other significant factors that persuade the exchange rate are speculation, change in competitiveness, government regulation, political stability and economic performance, expectation, government debt, relative strength of other currency. The motive of this paper is to analyze the factors influencing the fluctuation of exchange rate in Bangladesh. Every year Bangladesh export goods and services especially readymade garments, agricultural product, shrimp etc. in different country and also import from other country which affect exchange rate of this country. In recent past, the export performance of Bangladesh has been somewhat depressed. The export of Bangladesh has been grown up by 4.4% but the target was to achieve 8% during July-December 2016. Here the export of readymade garments was 4.4% and non RMG is 4.8% where the target was 8.1% and 7.4% respectively for fiscal year 2017. (The Daily Star). Balance of trade which has major impact on exchange rate fluctuation of any country is calculated by subtracting total

import from total export of the country. Total economic activity of any country has great impact on exchange rate. And this total economic activity is represented by the gross domestic product of any country. Inflation influences the exchange rate most which refers the rate at which the general level of prices for goods and services is increasing and, consequently, the buying power is decreasing. In an attempt to keep the excessive growth of prices to a minimum, Bangladesh Bank attempts to stop severe inflation, along with severe deflation. Most countries' central banks try to sustain an inflation of 2-3%. But the inflation of Bangladesh is larger than that level. On the other hand, interest rate is the rate at which a debtor for the use of money that they borrow from the creditor pays price. Monetary policy considers it as a vital tool and takes into account when dealing with variables like investment, inflation and unemployment. Remittance is a transfer of money sent by a foreign worker to a home country, which is playing an important role in the economies of many developing and low-income countries and one of the factors of influencing exchange rate. Changes in exchange rate have inevitable effects, with significances for prices, wages, interest rates, production levels, and employment opportunities. Fluctuations in the value of currencies of different economies have increased after the collapse of Bretton Woods System.

Objective of the Study:

The writing of this paper contains two objectives: General objective and Specific objective.

General Objective

The general objective of this analysis is to identify the factors affecting the fluctuation of exchange in Bangladesh.

Specific Objectives

Based on the general objective some specific objectives come forward too. The specific objectives are:

- To find out the nature of relationship between those factors and exchange rate.
- To find out the impact of each factor on exchange rate
- To identify the reason behind the change of exchange rate

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several factors determine exchange rates, and all are related to the trading relationship between two countries. And exchange rates are relative, and are expressed as a contrast of the currencies of two countries. The changes of exchange rate depend on different factors. Many researchers conducted different study to identify the factors that affects the exchange rate most. Patel et al (2014) conducted

analysis on factors influencing currency exchange rate, economical formulas and prediction models. The study shows main factors which are inducing currency rates, concentrating on economical formulas based on the economics theory to check health of the currency and useful prediction models for currency exchange rate. Rahman et al (2014) collected data for the period of 1990 to 2011 and investigate the determinants of exchange rates in Bangladesh economy by using simple single equation linear regression model (SELRM). The analysis find out that GDP growth rate, current account balance, interest and inflation rate are positively related with exchange rate. But GDP growth rate and current account balance are find out as the major determinants of exchange rate in Bangladesh economy. Kamal et al (2013) examines the factor that influences the exchange in Bangladesh greatest through the co integration approach. The study finds out the role of economic and non-economic factors in the determination of exchange rate in Bangladesh through the econometric analysis of determinants of exchange rate for US Dollar in terms of Bangladeshi currency, Relative stock of money and debt are positively and significantly affect the exchange rate. Relative foreign exchange reserve has negative correlation with exchange rate and it is significantly. The value of currencies is negatively influenced by political instability in case of Bangladesh. Empirical results demonstrate that exchange rate is strongly related with ratio stock of nominal money of respective currencies. Rise in the relative debt is another significant source affecting nominal exchange rate. One of the major causes of depreciation in the Bangladesh Taka against US Dollar is borrowing of the government from domestic and foreign sources. Saeed et al (2012) conducted econometric analysis of determinants of exchange rate for US Dollar in terms of Pakistani Rupee within the framework of monetary approach. To examine the long run and short run behavior of PKR/USD exchange rate and relationship of exchange rate behavior with relative monetary variables, monthly data from January 1982 to April 2010 for Pakistan relative to USA have been used. Relative stock of money and debt are positively and significantly related to exchange rate. Foreign exchange reserve has negative and significant relation with relative foreign exchange reserve. Political instability negatively affects the value of currencies in case of Pakistan. To the determine the PKR/USD exchange rate, relative short term interest rate and relative real GDP have no significant relation with exchange rate but they carry negative sign in accord with the sticky price monetary model. Empirical results specify that exchange rate is strongly associated with ratio stock of nominal money of respective currencies. Liew et al (2009) conducted analysis to examine the behavior of Baht (Thailand) and Yen (Japanese Currency) exchange rate in the context of flexible price monetary model. Empirical findings of the study suggest that exchange rate is efficiently determined by flexible price monetary model. Hsieh (2009) has analyzed the behavior of Indonesian Rupiah per unit of US Dollar. Results of prolonged Mundell-Fleming model of exchange rate determination designate that

relatively more real money aggregate, a relatively higher domestic interest rate, or a relatively more expected inflation rate causes real devaluation for Indonesian Rupiah. Higher ratio of governmental spending to GDP or higher stock prices lead to real appreciation in IDR/USD exchange rate. Lee-Lee et al (2007) examines the factors of exchange rate volatility from the macroeconomic perspective for four neighboring ASEAN economies that shown through the paper “Macroeconomic factors of exchange rate volatility Evidence from four neighboring ASEAN economies”. The study has scrutinized the link between macroeconomic factors and exchange rate volatility in both the short and the long run by applying econometrics techniques. This study finds the link between macroeconomic factors and exchange rate volatility in both the short and the long run for the selected economies. The empirical results indicate that a set of common factors seems to influence the exchange rate volatility, whereby the stock market is a great influence commonly found across countries. The Indonesian rupiah seems to be the most sensitive to the innovations in macroeconomic factors, while the Singapore dollar is the least. Janjua and Ahmed (2006) directed study to test purchasing power Parity for Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka. Mean reversion properties of real exchange rate series have been examined. No long run relationship happens between nominal exchange rate and relative price levels for Bangladesh. The evidence of co-integration for Sri Lanka and India was also quite weak. Co-integrating relationship for Pakistan between nominal exchange rate and relative price was significant both with respect to consumer price index and whole sale price index and lag length. Prior to adopting floating exchange rate regime, Islam (2003) argued that the economic and institutional prerequisites of a floating exchange rate regime are not met in Bangladesh. The behavior of nominal exchange rates of Bangladesh after its transition to the floating rate regime has been explained by some recent studies. Rahman et al (2001) analyzes real exchange rate behavior and exchange rate misalignments in Bangladesh. The study finds that real exchange rate and the macroeconomic fundamentals affecting real exchange rate form a co-integrating vector. It observes that trade liberalization and increase in debt service burden result in a real depreciation of currency; while increase in capital inflow, improvement in terms of trade, and increase in government consumption of non-tradable result in a real appreciation of currency. Nominal devaluation has been able to partly retain its effect to have a real devaluation in the short run. Papadopoulos and Zis (2000) study the determination of exchange rate by estimating Drachma/ECU rate applying integration technique, Impulse response and Variance decomposition analysis with monthly data from 1980 to 1991. Exchange rate variation appears to be dominated mainly by money and interest rate innovations. Siddiqui et al (1996) find out that rise in governmental expenditures leads to devaluation in real exchange rate through the analysis of the determinants of real exchange rate for Bangladesh. Coefficient of terms of trade (TOT) is positive and statistically

insignificant. The reason behind the real exchange rate appreciation is excess domestic credit creation. Openness has also contributed towards appreciation in exchange rate. Technological progress has negative sign but statistically insignificant. The equilibrium path determination of Real Exchange Rate has been significantly affected by both monetary variables and real sector variables. Campa & Goldberg (1993) studied that vitality in exchange rate is negatively related with investment and positive impact was found by Aizenman (1992). Exchange rate volatility affects the investment decision in long run but there is no significant relationships in short run so all countries who deal in long run investments focus on exchange rate fluctuations while considering a foreign direct investment.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Approach

For the convenience of the study, the descriptive and causal research approach has been applied to conduct the study and present the result so obtained.

3.2 Study Area and Population

In a statistical investigation, the interest usually lies in the assessment of the general magnitude and the study of variation with respect to one or more characteristics relating to individuals belonging to a group. This group of individuals under study is called population or universe. Thus in statistics, population is an aggregate of objects, animate or inanimate; under study (Gupta & Kapoor, 1994). The study area in this research is exchange rate and the factors affecting the exchange rate in Bangladesh.

3.3. Sampling

The sampling period is taken to prepare this thesis begins from January 2012 to December 2016. That means 60 months data of dependent and independent variables is taken as a sample which starts from January 2012 to December 2016.

3.4 Data Collection Procedure

To quantify the relationship between dependent variable and independent variable, data is collected by using secondary sources. The sources of data are Bangladesh economic indicator published by Bureau of Statistics of the Bangladesh, monthly publications of Bangladesh Bank and various publications of e-journal of Bangladesh.

3.5 Measurement of Variables

3.5.1. Dependent Variable

Exchange rate is the dependent variable. Monthly change of exchange rate is used. As exchange rate fluctuates on daily basis, monthly average exchange rate is obtained by adding together all the daily observations of a month and by dividing this total by the number of observations. And the formula is as follows:

$$A = \frac{\sum}{n}$$

A = average (or arithmetic mean) n = the number of terms (e.g., the number of items or numbers being averaged) xt = the value of each individual item in the list of numbers being averaged

3.5.2 Independent Variable

The independent variables which are the factors affecting the exchange of Bangladesh are inflation, interest rate, export, import, remittance, balance of payment and balance of trade. Fluctuation of each of the independent variable is observed during the sampling period from January 2012 to December 2016 to identify the impact of those fluctuations on exchange rate.

3.6 Software Used

MS Excel, Equation and SPSS-16.0 (Statistical Package for Social Science) is used for processing and analyzing the data.

3.7 Procedure of Data Analysis

The decisive part of this analysis is to find out the factors that influence the exchange rate in Bangladesh. Several statistical tools are used to analyze and evaluate the data. Correlation analysis is used to find out the relationship between dependent variable and independent variable. Correlation coefficient measures the strength and direction of relationship among variables. The impact of independent variable on dependent variable is analyzed by regression analysis. Because it is easy and more appropriate to find out the average probable change in dependent variable given a certain amount of change in independent variable with the help of regression. To analyze the impact of independent variables on dependent variable, the regression model is used which is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1$$

Where, Y = Dependent variable,

β_0 = Constant,

β_1 = Coefficient of independent variable

X_1 = Independent Variable

3.8 Research Hypotheses

After analyzing different literatures and objectives, the following hypotheses can be used:

H ₀₁	There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and inflation.
H ₀₂	There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and interest rate.
H ₀₃	There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and balance of payment.
H ₀₄	There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and balance of trade.
H ₀₅	There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and remittance.
H ₀₆	There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and export
H ₀₇	There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and import

Result Discussion and Findings

In this section, data has been examined based on different statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics has been conducted to present the information regarding variables. On the other hand, correlation analysis shows the whether the relationship exists or not between the variables and the nature of those relationship presented through scatter plot. The impact of independent variables on dependent variable is displayed through regression model.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis

The descriptive statistics analysis shows information regarding variables that influences the exchange rate and it also represents the information of exchange rate. Minimum, maximum, mean value and standard deviation of each independent variables and dependent variable has been shown through descriptive statistics table.

Table: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
Exchange Rate	60	77.4006	83.4233	78.79576	1.6237348
Inflation	60	5.51	10.96	7.0765	1.40743

Interest Rate	60	9.93	13.95	12.4798	1.31147
Balance of Payment*	60	-4387.6	-897.40	-2359.387	647.4063242
Balance of Trade**	60	-128.40	89.60	-69.9378	29.26516
Remittance***	60	951.37	1465.88	1201.1	116.38964
Export***	60	1765.1	3593	2534.465	398.7689590
Import**	60	113.9800	405.8200	288.9405	62.4245151
Valid N (listwise)	60				
<p>Note: * The value of balance of payment in BDT Crore. **The value of balance of trade and import in BDT billion. *** The value of export and remittance in US\$ million.</p>					

The descriptive table shows the maximum, minimum and mean values of all variables. But the standard deviation of balance of payment, balance of trade, remittance, export and import shows that distributions are well dispersed because deviation is larger and not close to zero. Standard deviation measures the absolute variation of distribution; here the greater the standard deviation, the greater the magnitude of the deviation of the values from their mean that means greater amount of variation among the observation. Such large standard deviation of balance of payment, balance of trade, remittance, export and import (647.4063242, 29.26516, 116.38964, 398.7689590 and 62.4245151 respectively) means a low degree of uniformity of the observations as well as homogeneity. On the other hand, exchange rate, inflation and interest rate have lower standard deviation than any other variables which indicate higher degree of uniformity of the observations as well as homogeneity.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is conducted to find out the strength and direction of relationship between variables. Here the correlation between exchange rate and each single variable that influences exchange is tested through hypothesis.

H01: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and inflation.

H11: There is significant relationship between exchange rate and inflation.

Table: Correlation between Exchange Rate and Inflation

Correlations			
		Exchange Rate	Inflation
Exchange Rate	Pearson Correlation	1	0.625**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	60	60
Inflation	Pearson Correlation	0.625*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table shows that the correlation coefficient between exchange rate and inflation is 0.625 which indicates strong (suggested by Evans, 1996) positive relationship between variables and it is close to 1.00. At 5% level of significant, the calculated significant value is less than accepted level of significant ($p < 0.05$) and it is highly significant. So the null hypothesis of no relationship between exchange rate and inflation is rejected. There is enough evidence to show that inflation is positively correlated with exchange rate.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and interest rate.

H₁₂: There is significant relationship between exchange rate and interest rate.

Table: Correlation between Exchange Rate and Interest Rate

Correlations			
		Exchange Rate	Interest Rate
Exchange Rate	Pearson Correlation	1	0.370**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.004
	N	60	60
Interest Rate	Pearson Correlation	0.370**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.004	
	N	60	60

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Hence, the null hypothesis of no relationship of exchange rate and interest is rejected. This, along with positive sign of r , indicates that interest rate is positively related to exchange rate. But the strength of relationship between variables is weak. The statistical significant level is less than accepted level of significant. There is enough evidence to show that exchange rate and interest rate are positively correlated, value is very significant (0.004) which is less than 0.01 and value r is coefficient 0.370.

H03: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and balance payment.

H13: There is significant relationship between exchange rate and balance of payment.

Table: Correlation between Exchange Rate and Balance of Payment

Correlations			
		Exchange Rate	Balance of Payment
Exchange Rate	Pearson Correlation	1	0.383**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.003
	N	60	60
Balance of Payment	Pearson Correlation	0.383**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table shows that $r = 0.383$ which indicates a weak positive relationship between exchange rate and balance of payment. Here, the statistical significant value is greater than the calculated value ($p < 0.05$). So null hypothesis is rejected. Then it states that, there is significant relationship between exchange rate and balance of payment.

Table: Correlation between Exchange Rate and Balance of Trade

H04: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and balance trade.

H14: There is significant relationship between exchange rate and balance of trade.

Correlations			
		Exchange Rate	Balance of Trade
Exchange Rate	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.215
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.099
	N	60	60
Balance of Trade	Pearson Correlation	-0.215	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.099	
	N	60	60

Table shows that $r = -0.215$ which indicates a weak negative relationship between exchange rate and balance of trade. Although there is weak negative relationship between variables, the statistical

H05: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and remittance.

H15: There is significant relationship between exchange rate and remittance.

significant value is less than the calculated value ($p > .05$). So null hypothesis is accepted. Then it states that, there is no significant relationship between exchange rate and balance of trade. There is no enough evidence to show the relationship between exchange rate and balance of trade.

Table: Correlation between Exchange Rate and Remittance

Correlations			
		Exchange Rate	Remittance
Exchange Rate	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.150
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.254
	N	60	60
Remittance	Pearson Correlation	-0.150	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.254	
	N	60	60

The correlation coefficient between exchange rate and remittance is -0.150 which indicates very weak and negligible negative relationship between variables. At 5% level of significant, the calculated significant value is greater than accepted level of significant ($p > 0.05$). So the null hypothesis of no relationship between exchange rate and remittance is accepted. There is no enough evidence to show that remittance is correlated with exchange rate.

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and export.

H₁₆: There is significant relationship between exchange rate and export.

Table: Correlation between Exchange Rate and Export

Correlations			
		Exchange Rate	Export
Exchange Rate	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.470**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	60	60
Export	Pearson Correlation	-0.470**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table shows that $r = -0.470$ which indicates a moderate negative relationship between exchange rate and export. That means export is negatively correlated with exchange rate and the statistical significant value is greater than the calculated value ($p < .05$). So null hypothesis is rejected. Then it states that, there is significant relationship between exchange rate and export and it is highly significant as the significant value is 0.00 which is less than 0.01. There is enough evidence to show the relationship between exchange rate and export

Table: Correlation between Exchange Rate and Import

H₀₇: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and import.

H₁₇: There is significant relationship between exchange rate and import.

Correlations			
		Exchange Rate	Import
Exchange Rate	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.421**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.001
	N	60	60
Import	Pearson Correlation	-0.421**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Hence, the null hypothesis of no relationship of exchange rate and import is rejected. This, along with negative sign of r , indicates that import is negatively related to exchange rate. And the strength of relationship between variables is moderate. The statistical significant level is less than accepted level of significant. There is enough evidence to show that exchange rate and import are negatively correlated, value is very significant (0.001) which is less than 0.01 and value r is coefficient -0.421.

4.3 Regression Analysis

The impact of changes of independent variables on the dependent variable has been analyzed through the regression. The regression analysis states whether the model is good fit or not. It also represents by how much dependent variable is changed through the one unit changes of independent variables.

Table 25: Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.693 ^a	0.480	0.410	1.2469196
a. Predictors: (Constant), Import, Balance of Trade, Remittance, Balance of Payment, Inflation, Export, Interest Rate				

The table presents R that means linear correlation coefficient, which measures the strength and the direction of a linear relationship between variables. The correlation coefficient in the table is 0.693, which is between 0.60 and 0.79. Therefore, there exists a strong positive relationship between independent variables (Import, Balance of Trade, Remittance, Balance of Payment, Inflation, Export, and Interest Rate) and exchange rate. On the other hand, the coefficient of determination that means R squared gives the proportion of variance of one variable that is predictable from other variable. Here R squared is 0.480, which means 48% of the total variation in exchange rate can be explained by variation of independent variables. The other 52% of total variation in exchange rate remains unexplained.

Table 26:ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	74.704	7	10.672	6.864	.000 ^a
	Residual	80.850	52	1.555		
	Total	155.554	59			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Import, Balance of Trade, Remittance, Balance of Payment, Inflation, Export, Interest Rate						
b. Dependent Variable: Exchange Rate						

The table shows that the calculated value of F as 6.864. But the critical value of F in a 5% level of significance at the degrees of freedom 7 and 52 is 2.208. As the calculated value is greater than the table value, the null hypothesis is rejected that there is no significant impact of independent variables on dependent variable. From the p value 0.00 which is less than .05 indicates that the model estimated by the regression procedure is only tending towards statistical significance and it is good fit. As exchange rate is dependent variable and import, balance of trade, remittance, balance of payment, inflation, export, interest rate are independent variable, the regression model are:

$$\text{Exchange Rate} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Inflation} + \beta_2 \text{ Interest Rate} + \beta_3 \text{ Balance of Payment} + \beta_4 \text{ Balance of Trade} + \beta_5 \text{ Remittance} + \beta_6 \text{ Export} + \beta_7 \text{ Import}$$

Where, β_0 = Constant, β_1 = Slope of Inflation,

β_2 = Slope of Interest Rate, β_3 = Slope of Balance of Payment,

β_4 = Slope of Balance of Trade, β_5 = Slope of Remittance,

β_6 = Slope of Export, β_7 = Slope of Import

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	80.518	3.356		23.990	0.000
	Inflation	0.575	0.152	0.498	3.774	0.000
	Interest Rate	-0.146	0.186	-0.118	-0.785	0.436
	Balance of Payment	7.810E-5	0.000	0.031	0.242	0.809
	Balance of Trade	-0.002	0.006	-0.041	-0.374	0.710
	Remittance	0.000	0.002	-0.008	-0.073	0.942
	Export	0.000	0.001	-0.209	-1.489	0.143
	Import	-0.006	0.003	-0.219	-1.997	0.051
a. Dependent Variable: Exchange Rate						

From the coefficient table the values of β_0 and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_7$ are found in the B column. The first value, 80.518, is the value of β_0 (labeled Constant). The second value, 0.575 is the value of β_1 (labeled as a slope of the independent variable Inflation) and the value of β_2 (slope of interest rate) is -0.146 and so on.

Thus, regression model for exchange rate:

<p>Exchange Rate = 80.518+ 0.575 Inflation- 0.146 Interest Rate + 0.0000781 Balance of Payment -0.002 Balance of Trade + 0.000 Remittance + 0.000 Export -0.006 Import</p>

The equation implies that a unit change in the independent variable (Inflation) causes the dependent variable (Exchange Rate) to change by an amount of 0.575. As β_1 is positive this indicates that the movement of the dependent variable (Exchange Rate) with the independent variable (Inflation) will be in the same direction. That is when the amount of inflation will increase exchange rate will also increase and vice versa. Balance of payment slightly change the exchange rate and the amount is 0.0000781. On the other hand, interest rate, balance of trade and import have negative impact on exchange rate. That means when interest rate, balance of trade and import increase by one unit, exchange rate will decrease by amount 0.146, 0.002 and 0.006 respectively and vice versa. But remittance and export have no impact on exchange rate at all.

CONCLUSION AND Findings

After analyzing the factors influencing the fluctuation of exchange in Bangladesh, it is lucid enough that inflation, interest rate, balances of payment, export and import influence the exchange rate. But

insignificant relation of balance of trade and remittance with exchange rate in Bangladesh. Between inflation and exchange rate, there exists positive correlation and the strength of association is strong. And inflation has greater impact on exchange rate than that of any other factors. Interest rate and balance of payment are also moderate and positive relation with exchange rate, where export and import have negative association with exchange rate. The association of balance of trade and remittance with exchange rate is also negative but it is insignificant. These factors are not enough to influence the exchange rate in Bangladesh. The study represents some specific factors those have numerical impact on exchange rate. But some factors those have impact on exchange rate cannot be measured numerically. Most of the time, they influences exchange rate in significantly than that of any other factors. Those some other factors which have greater impact on exchange rate in Bangladesh are gross domestic product, government debt, government regulation, political stability and performance, recession and speculation. The analysis reveals that inflation has greater impact on exchange rate than any other factor. So to efficiently manage the free floating exchange rate system in Bangladesh, Bangladesh Bank requires controlling inflationary pressure most than that of other factors.

5. Findings

Based on the objectives of this study, there are some findings after analyzing the collected data about the variables which are as follows:

5.1 Factors Influences the Exchange Rate

The analysis shows that some factors which influence the exchange rate most are inflation, interest rate, gross domestic product, balance of payment, balance of trade, remittance, export and import etc. In spite of those factors, there are some other factors that influence exchange rate such as gross domestic product, government debt, government regulation, political stability and performance, recession and speculation and they are somewhat positively or negatively related with exchange rate.

5.2 Nature of Relationship

The study shows significant relationship of exchange rate with inflation, interest rate and balance of payment which is positive. Here the strength of relationship between inflation and exchange rate is strong. And the strength of relationship of balance of payment and interest rate with exchange rate is weak. There is no significant relationship of balance of trade and remittance with exchange rate of Bangladesh. On the other hand, export and import have highly significant relationship with exchange rate and they are negatively correlated. But the strength of relationship of export and import with exchange rate is moderate.

5.3 Impact of Each Independent Variable

Among all other independent variables, inflation has greater impact on exchange rate that means in one unit change in inflation, exchange rate will change by 0.575 which is greater than all other variables' impact on exchange rate. The impact is positive. In spite of having significant relationship of export and import with exchange rate, export shows no impact on exchange rate and import shows slight negative impact on exchange rate. Interest rate and balance of trade have negative impact on exchange rate that means if interest rate and balance of trade increase, exchange rate will decrease.

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